

Stage-by-stage evaluation of a biomedical system regarding its electromagnetic susceptibility

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Abstract—Electromagnetic interference has been the cause for many failures of medical devices over the past years. All these devices have to undergo a series of tests to validate its conformity regarding electromagnetic compliance. This work presents the results of research done on a certified biomedical system to identify the potential improvements of such an apparatus concerning interference. A first evaluation of the electrodes alone shows how the material they are made of can play a role on how easily electromagnetic interference couples to these. Furthermore, the electronic circuits of the system are also evaluated as their role is to filter all the undesired signals and leave only the biosignals. Finally, a real world use case scenario is replicated inside the anechoic chamber in the presence of a disturbing signal with results showing that by applying a signal modulated at a frequency in the range of the biosignals sensors pass band is enough to rend its acquired signal worthless.

Index Terms—Electrocardiogram; Electrodes; Electromagnetic; Immunity; Interference; Radiated; Susceptibility; Wearables.

I. INTRODUCTION

For a medical device to be placed in the European Market, CE marking is required to show the Medical Device Regulation has been respected [1]. To do so, a common way of demonstrating it is to show compliance with the relevant requirements. When it comes to electromagnetic compatibility, the international standards IEC60601 cover a series of general and particular standards relative to biomedical devices safety and basic performance in the presence of electromagnetic disturbances at home or in healthcare facilities. [2]. These are devices designed to work with signals of low amplitudes and low frequencies [3]; they are complex and the possibility of coupling of radiated interference exists from the device all the way to the electrodes connected to a patient [4].

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement No. 955.816.

This work has been partially supported by Spanish "Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación" under project PID2019-106120RBC31/AEI/10.13039/501100011033

In this work, we want to verify the susceptibility of biosignals acquisition devices by conducting research stage by stage on the BITalino (r)evolution [5] (hereinafter referred to as BITalino). It is intended to record low potential signals such as the electrocardiogram (ECG), the electromiogram (EMG) and the electroencephalogram (EEG) by the means of surface electrodes. In this paper multiple types of electrodes are evaluated, using a novel proposed methodology for individual analysis of the electrode. Afterwards, the ECG measurement circuitry to which the electrodes are connected is evaluated in a TEM cell in terms of electrical and magnetic coupling. Finally, the device is placed in the anechoic chamber where a realistic scenario is replicated in order to estimate how the system would behave in the presence of electromagnetic interference modifying the characteristics of the signal used as disturbance. The findings of this work are presented in the last section.

II. MATERIALS

A. Electrodes

In this work, the first point of interest was the influence of electrodes and how their behaviour changes in presence of electromagnetic disturbances. For that, three electrodes of different materials were used, namely: silver, graphene and carbon. The electrodes, presented in Figure 1, are dry electrodes printed on a thin flexible film and they are intended to replace the commonly used gelled Silver/Silver-Chloride (Ag/AgCl) electrodes on long term monitoring. They were studied in previous works where its reliability and performance were evaluated [6]. The results have shown evidence of the electrodes ability to be used as a replacement for the current Ag/AgCl gelled electrodes [7], [8]. However, with the technologies available nowadays, the systems designed to acquire biosignals such as the ECG, are diminishing in size, making the electrode leads one of the main points of coupling for electromagnetic interference [4] and the principal focus in this work.

Fig. 1. Electrodes for biosignals acquisition. From left to right: carbon, graphene and silver

Fig. 2. EuroTEM

Fig. 3. Electrode placement

B. EuroTEM

Given the small size of the electrodes, the studies on the electromagnetic susceptibility of these were initially done in a TEM cell (Transverse ElectroMagnetic cell) called EuroTEM and presented in Figure 2 [9]. This particular TEM cell has the ability of generating a constant field inside the chamber with variable polarization: vertical or horizontal. Before starting the susceptibility tests with the electrodes, the EuroTEM had to be calibrated. In fact, the electrical field in the chamber is not constant across the frequency spectrum for which the chamber was designed, which in this case is between 10 MHz and 1 GHz. Therefore, an electrical field probe (FL7006) was used to analyse the field inside the chamber in all three axis and the measurements obtained were used to adjust the cell RF input, so that the generated field would have the same value across the entire spectrum.

III. METHODS

A. Electrodes Susceptibility

Once the calibration measurements have been done inside the chamber, the electrodes could be placed inside it to start the tests. For these measurements, the electrodes were placed in the center of the constant electrical field volume in the vertical position, facing directly the source of the interference as illustrated in Figure 3. The cable to which they were connected was ran inside a metallic pipe parallel to the wave propagation direction and therefore perpendicular to both the electrical and magnetic field. Furthermore, this pipe was connected to the ground of the chamber providing shielding to the wire connected to the electrode. Outside of the chamber, the electrode wire was connected to a coaxial cable leading to a spectrum analyser Rohde & Schwarz FSH3¹. This spectrum analyser was set to register the signal coupled to the electrode along the entire frequency range.

¹Rohde & Schwarz FSH3 Handheld Spectrum Analyzer - rohde-schwarz.com

Fig. 4. Electronic scheme of the acquisition device

B. Influence of Disturbances on the ECG Amplifier

The signals captured by the electrodes (both the biosignal under study and interference) will enter the acquisition device (Figure 4). This presents a high gain to amplify the very low amplitude biosignals ($\sim 1\text{mV}$) [10], [11]. Typically, environment noise presents greater amplitudes than the signal we are trying to capture and, for that reason, it is important that the instrumentation amplifier used to amplify the signal is capable of rejecting noise, be it differential or common mode. To evaluate these two sources of noise, a protocol was established for the evaluation of both. This allowed to estimate how the interference captured by the electrodes propagate across the sensor. It consisted of placing a metallic structure inside the EuroTEM connected to the two amplifier inputs of the BITalino's ECG, placed outside the chamber so that the disturbances generated by the field inside would only be captured by this structure. The latter, represented in Figure 5, intended to simulate the electrode leads placed on a human body using two metallic wires connected to a $1\text{ k}\Omega$ resistor. The disturbing signal was produced with a HAMEG HM8134 signal generator, sweeping the entire frequency range of the EuroTEM, from 10 MHz to 1 GHz. The measurements were done for three different positions of the structure, each one of them allowing to evaluate one factor at a time. Figure 5 shows the three positions in which the structure was placed: the first one, A, was intended to maximize coupling from both magnetic and electrical fields; the second, B, minimized the magnetic field coupling through the loop it makes; finally, the third one, C, minimized the electrical field coupling and maximized the magnetic field entering the loop. For each of these positions, three measurements were done: common mode voltage of each input of the amplifier and differential mode voltage. A schematic representation of the system is given in Figure 4. These measurements were done using the spectrum analyser in order to see how the different frequencies would affect the system.

C. Effect of Interference During an Acquisition

These first two steps in the evaluation of the system made it clear that it is possible that the quality of the acquired signal is compromised by the disturbances to which it is susceptible. All these tests were applied to the system as a product and not in a real world scenario. This last step aims to verify how the electrodes would behave in a real use case in the presence of a disturbing signal. This meant

Fig. 5. Positioning of the structure to evaluate electrical and magnetic field. From left to right: A, B, and C

preparing an acquisition setup inside an anechoic chamber where a simulated electrocardiogram would be acquired with the setup in question. To replace the human body, a tissue mimicking material was used where the simulated signal was injected. This consisted of an agar phantom which is widely used to simulate the human tissue [12], [13]. The phantom was prepared using a concentration of 40g of agar per liter of a saline solution consisting of water with sodium chloride. To prepare the phantom, 400ml of saline solution were heated, to which 16g of agar were added while mixing with a magnetic stirrer. Before starting the experiment, however, it was decided that the influence of the agar should be evaluated. In fact, it is not only the equipment that is affected by electromagnetic interference. The disturbance can be coupled to the human body increasing the amount of noise at the input of the system.

1) *Influence of the agar in the measurements:* To verify the influence of the agar in the measurements, two acquisitions were made with and without agar. To evaluate the influence of the latter, the electrode would be placed on its surface. In both cases, the electrode was facing the antenna in the same place and position, while connected to a spectrum analyser via a coaxial cable ensuring shielding of the entire wire leading to the electrode. During the trials with the agar, the phantom would be placed between the electrode and the incident wave so that the latter would reach the phantom first and not the electrode directly.

2) *Simulated ECG acquisition:* Inside the anechoic chamber, the setup was prepared for the acquisition with the agar phantom mimicking the skin where the bio electrical signal from the heart propagates and can be read by surface biopotential electrodes. Embedded in the agar phantom, two metallic electrodes were inserted. These were connected to an Agilent 33120A arbitrary waveform generator creating a differential ECG signal to be measured by the electrodes under test. The phantom was separated into two pieces, and a $1k\Omega$ resistor was placed in between the two to avoid short circuiting the signal injected. The acquisition device used in this setup was a BITalino. For this study the focus was on the ECG as it is the most simulated signal by the commonly available simulators. Furthermore, the device is able to read an electrocardiogram with two electrodes only. In this case, one of the electrodes was the one under test, and the other electrode was a commonly used Ag/AgCl gelled electrode². Each electrode was placed on the surface of each piece of

Fig. 6. Setup inside the anechoic chamber

TABLE I
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE INTERFERING SIGNAL APPLIED TO THE DEVICE

Modulating frequency	Electrical field
1.3 kHz	3 V/m
30 Hz	
20 Hz	
1.3 kHz	10 V/m
30 Hz	
20 Hz	

agar. The signal acquired by the BITalino was streamed via Bluetooth to a laptop placed inside the anechoic chamber, where the signal acquired was being displayed and recorded live using the software OpenSignals (r)evolution³. The setup used is presented in Figure 6.

A wired camera pointed at the computer screen allowed to visualize the signal being acquired live from the outside. Several disturbing signals were applied during this study to evaluate how each factor would affect the overall quality of the signal. The variables in the signal were the modulating frequency and the amplitude level of the electrical field; Table I summarizes the characteristics of each interference applied over the entire series of tests.

IV. RESULTS

A. Electrodes Susceptibility

The measurements done to the electrodes individually inside the EuroTEM were very conclusive as to which material would be more susceptible to electromagnetic interference as evidenced by Figure 7. These have been previously presented in conference [14] and show clear evidence on the influence of the material, with regard to the coupling of radiated interference on the electrodes with the silver electrodes presenting a higher susceptibility across the range of frequencies taken into consideration. The fact that this material is the most commonly used in biomedical instrumentation and its proneness to radiated coupling, led us to further investigate how these

²Covidien Kendall ECG Electrodes-Product datasheet

³OpenSignals (r)evolution - Available at www.pluxbiosignals.com

Fig. 7. Susceptibility of the electrodes

Fig. 8. Differential voltage and common mode voltage

disturbances propagate in the circuitry where the electrodes are placed.

B. Influence of Disturbances on the ECG Sensor

Following the methodology introduced in Section III-B, we obtained the curves presented in Figure 8 showing the two common mode voltages obtained by placing the structure in position B, and the differential mode voltage obtained with position C. The values of the two common mode voltages are very close to each other, given the similarity of the two wires to which the electrical field was coupled. Furthermore, the effect of the common mode voltages, originated by the electrical field, is overall predominant over the differential voltage, which was originated by the magnetic field. However, these values change with the polarization of the incident wave and its orientation with regard to the loop created. In a real case scenario, however, where the electrodes are placed in the body with short leads, and considering the contribution of the human body to the total interference coupling, the polarization of the wave plays little to no role.

C. Effect of Interference During an Acquisition

1) *Influence of the agar in the measurements:* In the last part of these tests, we were interested in knowing how much more degraded can a signal get when performing an acquisition. For that, we looked at the results from the experiments in the anechoic chamber using the agar phantom and with the electrodes alone in the presence of a 10 V/m electrical field. Figure 9 illustrate the latter and the results are in agreement with what had previously been demonstrated with the methodology described in Section III-A. Once again, the silver electrodes have proven to be more susceptible to the disturbance, which was also verified when the agar was introduced. As Figure 10 shows, the levels of disturbance perceived by the electrodes are amplified by as much as 10 dBm, especially in the lower frequencies, and the silver electrode is once again the most susceptible. This demonstrates

two things: the first being how the agar (and, by extension, the human body), in general, makes the system more prone to electromagnetic interference on both materials. Secondly, the results provide yet more evidence on how the material used with the electrodes plays a role on the interference received by a system.

2) *Simulated ECG acquisition:* Finally, and since the silver electrodes have proved to be the more susceptible to electromagnetic interference, we used them to prepare the setup for the real world scenario analysis, as to have the most challenging conditions. Once the setup was in place, we started by radiating the system with a 10 V/m disturbing signal, i.e., modulated at 1 kHz sweeping the frequencies from 80 MHz up to 1 GHz. The output of the device was being scoped by the spectrum analyser at the same time that the acquired signal was displayed on the computer screen. As expected, the disturbance was not enough to generate any malfunction on the device. However, with the spectrum analyser, we noticed that the system was more susceptible around the 270 MHz frequency range. For this reason, we set the disturbing signal at this value and evaluated how the modulating frequency played a role on the output using the values given in Table I.

In Figure 11 we can see the signal acquired by the BITalino with a non modulated 270 MHz signal. With no surprise, there is no interference noticeable on the ECG PQRST wave at the acquisition stage, which remained true even with a modulation of 1 kHz. However, this was not the case with a modulating frequency of 1.3 kHz. In a collaboration work with Bastian et al [15], submitted for review towards the proceedings of EMC Europe 2023, a risk analysis of the system shows that, by using a slightly different frequency for the modulating signal, the behaviour of the device under test would be very different. In this case, with a modulating frequency of 1.3KHz, it was already possible to see some deformations on the signal acquired at 3V/m (Figure 12). These became even more noticeable when the field strength

Fig. 9. Comparison of graphene and silver electrodes' susceptibility

Fig. 10. Agar influence on the electrodes.

increased from 3 V/m to 10 V/m, as evidenced by Figure 13. These devices are designed to acquire physiological signals with have very low frequencies and therefore low pass filters are employed. For this reason, even in strong fields, these devices are able to reject most noise in high frequencies. Therefore, we decided to decrease the modulating frequency to values in the vicinity of physiological signals, and the effect was immediate. At 20 Hz, even with a 3 V/m field (Figure 14), it was possible to see the modulating signal on the output of the sensor since these frequencies are comprised in the pass band of the filter on the sensor. The consequences of these interferences could mask the smaller fiducials needed by a physician to analyse an electrocardiogram properly, even though the R-peaks are still clear and enough to extract the heart rate. As soon as the field strength increases to 10 V/m however, the consequences are much more accentuated. As illustrated by Figure 15, the smaller waves in the ECG (P, Q, S and T waves) are almost completely submerged in noise

Fig. 11. Acquired ECG in the presence of a disturbing signal without modulation

due to the modulating frequency. Furthermore, the effects now extend to the overall signal where even the amplitude of the R-peaks is affected.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, an extensive analysis of a system for biomedical applications regarding its electromagnetic susceptibility was performed. A stage-by-stage approach, starting at the electrode level, allowed us to conclude that these play an important role in the amount of electromagnetic noise that is received by the device and more particularly by its sensor analog frontend. Reproducing the same evaluation with the electrodes placed on an agar phantom mimicking the human body showed that, independently of the electrode's material, the presence of the phantom amplifies the levels of noise reaching the amplifier's inputs. The latter showed resilience in the conditions stipulated by current standards. A deeper analysis of the system in the anechoic chamber showed that in different conditions than those covered by current recommendations, the results of immunity tests can vary dramatically rendering the device performance insufficient for its basic functioning. By varying the modulating frequency of the signal used as a disturbance for the tests, major interference appeared at the output of the amplifier especially when these fell into the passing band of this kind of device. These are intended to filter high frequencies (above 500 Hz or less depending on the sensor), whereas the most common practice for radiated immunity tests validates frequencies in the range of MHz. However, not only should the modulated signal be considered, but the modulating frequency should also be regarded as a key factor in potential offenders for the systems under test.

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Fig. 12. Acquired ECG in the presence of a 3V/m disturbing signal modulated at 1.3 kHz

Fig. 13. Acquired ECG in the presence of a 10V/m disturbing signal modulated at 1.3 kHz

Fig. 14. Acquired ECG in the presence of a 3V/m disturbing signal modulated at 20 Hz

Fig. 15. Acquired ECG in the presence of a 10V/m disturbing signal modulated at 20 Hz

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